

Effect of Employees' Extra Role Behavior on the Performance of Food and Beverage Manufacturing Firms in Enugu, State

¹Okechukwu, E. Uzoamaka, ²Onyia, Ngozi Augustina and ³Okolie Jonathan Ibekwe

Department of Business Administration, Enugu State University of Science and Technology

Abstract

The study was to examine the effect of employee's extra role behavior on the performance of food and beverage of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives employee includes; employee's Sportsmanship on the customer satisfaction and altruism of employees on the team performance of food and beverage of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. A survey of research design was adopted for the study. Data for the study was purely a primary source of data. The tool of analysis used is the SPSS v.20 with emphasis on correlation analysis (r), coefficient of determination (R²), F-test (ANOVA) and regression coefficients for fitting the model specifications. The result revealed that, employee's sportsmanship has a significantly positive impact customer satisfaction at p-value (R=0.824, p-value<0.001); and altruism of employee has significant impact on team performance at p-value = (R=0.903, p-value<0.001) on the performance of food and beverage of manufacturing firms for the period. Based on the finding, the study concluded that employee's sportsmanship, and altruism of employee all has significant impact on the performance of food and beverage of manufacturing firms for the period. The study recommends that, employees should sustain the employee sportsmanship and altruism as a means of holding on to the significant impact it has on customer satisfaction and team performance in order to enhance the firm overall performance.

Keywords *Employees' Extra Role Behavior; Performance; Food and Beverage Manufacturing Firms*

Citation Okechukwu, E. U., Onyia, N. A. & Okolie, J. I. (2023). Effect of Employees' Extra Role Behavior on the Performance of Food and Beverage Manufacturing Firms in Enugu, State. *Journal of Business Research and Statistics*, 5(1), 1-11 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7870060>

Introduction

Currently, organizations are required to improve their performance. To deal with this condition, human resources should be the center of attention to enable organizations explore their potentials. Individual-level performance draws upon those things that have to do with their jobs, or in-role performance, and those things that add value but which aren't part of their formal job description. These "extras" are called extra-role performance or organizational citizenship behaviors (OCBs). At this point, it is probably simplest to consider an in-role performance as having productivity and quality dimensions associated with certain standards that individuals must meet to do their job. In contrast, extra-role behaviors can be understood as individual behaviors that are beneficial to the organization and are discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognized by the formal reward system (Organ, 1988). Extra-role-behavior is a discretionary consent of an individual to behave beyond the formal lines of role expectation and work for the benefit and effectiveness of the organization. It involves activities that are optional in nature (helping others), which is not straight forwardly or clearly required by the formal reward system, but does promote overall managerial efficiency (Becker and Kernan, 2016). Extra-role-behavior which is also referred to as organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) is a term that's used to describe all the positive and constructive employee actions and behaviors that aren't part of their formal job description. It's anything that employees do, out of their own free will that supports their colleagues and benefits the organization as a whole. Extra-role-behavior is not something that's required from employees to do their job and it's not part of their contractual tasks. Podsakoff et al (2019) define extra-role behavior as flexible behavior, not directly valued by the organization's formal reward system, but as a whole, contributes to the organizational effectiveness such as helping coworkers. Organ et al. (2005) defines Extra-Role Behavior as behavior that is discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognized by a formal reward system and that in aggregate promotes the effective functioning of an organization. Examples of this discretionary behavior include cooperation with peers, performing extra duties without complaint, punctuality, volunteering and helping others (altruism), using time efficiently, conserving resources, sharing ideas and positively representing the organization (Turnipseed and Rassuli, 2005). Research indicates that employee attitudes, such as job satisfaction, are expressed through extra-role behaviors for which employees have volition and discretion. In essence, employees respond to supportive treatment from their organizations with organizational citizenship behaviors. Employee extra may be a crucial aspect that contributes to an organization's previous presence. As a result, it is critical for manufacturing organizations to comprehend the aspects that completely and forcefully support in fostering this complementary conduct within the organization.

Statement of the Problem

Employee extra role behavior can maximize the efficiency and performance of both the employee and the firm that ultimately contribute to the effective functioning of an organization. The knowledge and understanding of behavior are very important because it does not only ruin the individual performance but also create strong impact on the performance of others. Nevertheless, human behavior differs and cannot be the same in different situations. Different people behave differently in same situation and this different behavior could be based on intrinsic features, relationship to the situation, and perception of environmental aspects and other factors that influence the behavior. Employee with the best genetic features may possess positive attitude towards job; which may be influenced by the behavior of peers and other team members. Additionally, lack of sportsmanship is likely to have harmful effects on groups cohesiveness and make the atmosphere in the workplace less attractive for cooperation; and lead to poor survival of the manufacturing firms. There can be some possible drawbacks and difficulties to altruism, like: it can sometimes create risk. People may engage in altruistic acts that can place them in danger and neglecting their own needs and desires. Based on these, it has necessitated the study on the effect of employee's extra role behavior on the performance of food and beverage of manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the effect of employee's extra role behavior on the performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Assess the effect of employee's sportsmanship on the employees' job satisfaction of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State.
- ii. Evaluate the effect of Altruism on employees' output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Statement of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were used for the study

1. Sportsmanship does not have significant effect on employees' job satisfaction of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State?
2. Altruism does not have significant effect on employees' output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Extra Role Behavior

Extra-role behavior (ERB) is a construct similar to OCB that was first defined by (Organ, Podsakoff, and MacKenzie, 2006). ERB is defined as "behavior that tries to benefit the organization while exceeding existing role expectations" (Organ et al., 2006). While OCB and ERB are similar in many ways, there are some significant differences. Whistle blowing and principled organizational dissent are two concepts found in ERB that are not found in OCB. Whistle blowing is the act of one employee reporting unethical or illegal practices to authorities (Organ et al., 2006). Some of the extra role performance conducts are: assisting coworkers with a process associated hassle; accepting orders without fuss; tolerating temporary impositions without grievance; maintaining cleanliness and bodily hygiene of the place of job; promoting a work weather that is tolerable and minimizes the distractions created by means of interpersonal war; and defensive and holding organizational sources etc. (Bateman & Organ, 2015). Extra-role behavior (ERB is discretionary consent of an individual to behave beyond the formal lines of role expectation and work for the benefit and effectiveness of the organization. It involves activities that are discretionary in nature (such as helping others), which is not straightforwardly or clearly required by the formal reward system, but does promote overall managerial efficiency (Becker and Kernan, 2016). Role performance behaviors are certain practices of specialists, which are not part of their formal work necessities as they cannot be endorsed or fundamental in progress for a given work but they offer assistance within the smooth working of the organ. Organ et al. (2005) defines Extra-role behavior as behavior that is discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognized by a formal reward system and that in aggregate promotes the effective functioning of an organization. Examples of this discretionary behavior include cooperation with peers, performing extra duties without complaint, punctuality, volunteering and helping others, using time efficiently, conserving resource, sharing ideas and positively representing the organization (Turnipseed and Rassuli, 2005; Organ 1988). Extra-role behavior are behaviors that employees are not explicitly rewarded for exhibiting nor punished for not exhibiting. They are behaviors for which employees do not receive training to perform. Moreover, Schnake (1991) opine that, pro-social ethical behaviors such as helping new employees to understand the internal workings of the organization, assisting co-workers complete their jobs, attending meetings and volunteering to do things in excess of job descriptions are some of the behaviors that can be associated with OCB. These non-traditional behaviors are on-the-job behaviors that are not usually captured by traditional job descriptions (Moorman, 1991).

Types of Employees' Extra Role Behavior:

Human behavior is a capacity of mental, physical, emotional and social activities experienced during the different stages of human life and influenced by culture, society, values, morals, ethics and genetics. Cascio (2003) explained that human behavior cannot be same in different situations and different organizations. Examples of this discretionary behavior include cooperation with peers, performing extra duties without complaint, punctuality, volunteering and helping others (altruism), using time efficiently, conserving resource, sharing ideas, sportsmanship and positively representing the organization (Turnipseed and Rassuli, 2005).

Sportsmanship

Put simply, sportsmanship is about an employee's ability to be a good loser. It's about being able to deal with situations that do not go as planned – or negative surprises – and to not demonstrate negative behavior when that happens. An example of good sportsmanship in the workplace is an employee who is temporarily taking over the

tasks of a team member who broke his leg and will be on sick leave for a few weeks. While this considerably increases this employee's workload, she isn't complaining about it to her colleagues because she knows it's a temporary situation and that she's taking one for the team (to stick with the sports jargon).

Altruism

Altruism is self-motivated effort to help one another to sort out challenges in the working place for the progress of an organization or firms: The availability of altruists makes office to be livelier and more active. Workers will be more dedicated to their duties and reduction in employee turnover. It is observed that people who assist others becomes happier at work than people who do not care about helping others. (Zelenski, Steven, and David 2017) state that their findings make simple but clear point concerning altruism is not a form of martyrdom, but operates for many as part of a healthy psychological reward system. Being spurred to assist and accepting your work makes a contrast and is related with incredible joy in all investigation. The value of relationship in the place of work, creates room for stronger support to motivate employee 's productivity and make him/her more relaxed and energetic about their work. It has been observed that assisting others have many positive effects that elevate the morale of those doing the job and also increase the happiness among other challenges of the organization. Becker and Kernan (2016) posit that by creating chains of events that carry positive meaning for others, positive output that carry positive meaning for others, positive output for the organization will increase.

Performance

Performance is an ability (both physical & psychological) to perform a particular task in a specific method that can be evaluated as excellent, average or low in scale. The word of Performance is usually used to explain various aspects such as performance of organization, performance of employees and performance of individual. Campbell, McCloy, Oppler & Sager, 1993, demonstrated two dimensions of performance; first is the behavioral aspect and second is outcome performance aspect. The first aspect behavior is supposed to be matched to the situation and specification of job. Those behavioral are expected to be converted into accomplishing the organizational goals and objectives and this is the outcome aspect which is the second dimension of performance. The idea of organizational performance is the evaluation of an organization's dreams and objectives with its actual performance in three distinct regions: economic performance, marketplace performance and shareholder cost. Financial performance refers to an organization's result with regard to return on investment and return on assets. The market performance refers to a business enterprise 's capacity to set a rate that returns an inexpensive amount to providers. In addition, marketplace overall performance refers to the potential to make and distribute their outputs in the maximum cost powerful manner and to set a fee that returns an affordable amount. Team performance focuses on aspects of work that are best accomplished by teams of individuals working together. Task proficiency is another indicator of good performance as team members who are proficient in their tasks and are associated with higher performance levels. These teams may be reporting to the same individual or maybe cross-functional in nature. In some cases, they are permanent and in others, they exist for the duration of the project at hand.

Employees' Job Satisfaction

Employee satisfaction has a positive persuasion on organizational performance. Beside this, firm profitability has a reasonable non-recursive effect on employee satisfaction. Employee satisfaction plays a considerable role in enhancing the firm profitability and improving operational performance of organizations and quality of good and services (Marija, 2022).

Employee's Output

Employees' output refers to employee productivity, also known as productivity in the workplace or workplace productivity. It is the measure of an individual employee's output. For example, a company that produces artistic bottles will want to know how many artistic bottles one employee can manufacture in a specific period of time – this number is the individual employee's output (Marija, 2022).

Theoretical Framework

Needs Theory of Employee Behaviors

The Needs theory of employee behaviors were propounded by Maslow Abraham H. (1970), Human needs are numerous and often described as insatiable. These needs create a feeling of deficiency in the individuals and drive them to behave in ways that will likely lead to the fulfillment of these needs. Need theory of employee behavior was developed by Abraham Maslow in 1970. Maslow arranged human needs in the order of importance to include basic or survival needs (physiological needs, safety needs and belongingness) and growth needs (self-esteem and self-actualization). The survival needs are the most important and then the growth needs. These needs are arranged such that if the lower level or survival needs are not fulfilled, they continue to motivate and direct behavior towards their fulfillments. Consequently, as an individual fulfils his basic needs, the next need on the hierarchy takes precedence and begins to motivate until fulfillments. This process follows the satisfaction progression principle. Maslow (1970), employee needs include generous pay, job security, acceptance and recognition, self-esteem and self-actualization and the satisfaction of these needs is the basic motive behind all work behaviors. Employees experience satisfaction with jobs that provides avenues to meet their needs. It has been noted from this study that job satisfaction is an antecedent of desirable work behaviors and performances.

Empirical Review

Hasan, Mehmood, and Syed (2014) examined the Impacts of Employee's Job Performance Behavior and Organizational Culture on Organizational Productivity in Pharmaceutical Industries in Karachi. The calculated chi-square values in both cases are higher than the tabulated values. The study provides evidences of a strong positive impact of employee's job performance behavior and culture prevailing in the organization on productivity and job performance of employees, and also recommends bringing improvement in the employee culture in order to bring improvement to productivity. Ibojo, and Asabi. (2014) examined the effect of Compensation Management on Employees Performance in the Manufacturing Sector. The data was analyzed using inferential and descriptive statistics. While the hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The results shows that there is a significant relationship between good welfare service and employees' performance. It also shows that there is a significant relationship between compensation management and improved productivity.

Diah (2019) examined the effect of Servant Leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior: Role of Trust in Leader as a Mediation and Perceived Organizational Support as a moderation. This study aims to examine the role of trust in leaders (TIL) as a mediating variable and perceived organizational support (POS) as a moderating variable on the effect of SL on OCB. A total of 238 respondents were collected in the current study in various regions of Indonesia. The results showed that SL had a significant positive effect on OCB. POS was also reported to significantly moderate the effect of SL on OCB. In addition, it was unexpectedly reported that TIL did not mediate the effect of SL on OCB. Diane, Abbie, Benson and Stacie. (2013), Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Career Outcomes: The Cost of Being a Good Citizen. Results based on archival data from 3,680 employees in a professional services firm lend some support for these ideas. Specifically, time spent on task performance was more important than OCB in determining all four career outcomes. Further, controlling for time spent on task performance, employees who spent more time on OCB had lower salary increases and advanced more slowly than employees who spent less time on OCB. These findings suggest that relationships between OCB and outcomes are more complex than originally thought and that boundary conditions may apply to conclusions drawn about the outcomes of OCB.

Nnamani, Ozobu, and Ejim (2015) The study investigated the Effect of Employee Motivation on Organizational Performance of selected manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The study used descriptive statistics to answer three research questions posed for the study. The Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient was used to test the three hypotheses that guided the study. The result obtained from the analysis showed that there existed Relationship between employee motivation and the organizational performance. The study revealed that extrinsic motivation given to workers in an organization has a significant influence on the workers performance. Tung-Liang (2014) explored the effect of salary on altruistic behavior and job performance and the mediating effect of altruistic behavior in Taiwan. With teams and players of the NBA 2011-12 Playoffs as the sample, the regression analysis is

adopted to verify the hypotheses. It is found from the results that salary has a significant positive impact on altruistic behavior as well as job performance. Meanwhile, altruistic behavior has a significant positive impact on job performance and partly exerts mediating effect on the relationship between salary and job performance. Mbah, Ede, and Ugochukwu, (2017) investigated the effect of Organizational Citizenship behaviors on the performance of manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria. The research survey design was used. The data were analyzed using f-statistics (ANOVA) tool. The result showed that employee job satisfaction has positive effect on the productivity of manufacturing firm in South East, Nigeria; leadership supportiveness has positive effect on the survival of manufacturing firm in South East, Nigeria.

Nathan, Steven, Philip, and Brian (2009) examined Individual- and Organizational-Level Consequences of Organizational Citizenship Behaviors: A Meta-Analysis. Results, based on 168 independent samples (N = 51,235 individuals), indicated that OCBs are related to a number of individual-level outcomes, including managerial ratings of employee performance, reward allocation decisions, and a variety of withdrawal-related criteria (e.g., employee turnover intentions, actual turnover, and absenteeism). In addition, OCBs were found to be related (k = 38; N = 3,611 units) to a number of organizational-level outcomes (e.g., productivity, efficiency, reduced costs, customer satisfaction, and unit-level turnover). Natalie, Christopher & Hojun (2020) examined the effects of employees' extra-role behaviors on desired organizational outcomes in sport. An assessment of innovative work behaviors and organizational citizenship behaviors of Minor League Baseball team front office employees was conducted as organizations planned for an upcoming season. An empirical model controlling for extraneous factors was developed and tested. Results revealed organizational citizenship behaviors of front office employees positively affected attendance during the season for Triple-A and Double-A level franchises. Erkubilay & Şentürk (2020) determined the effect of altruism as a behavior, peer support and leader support on employee voice. The data were obtained from the employees working in Bolu Forest Regional Directorate and Forest Management Directorates affiliated to Bolu Forest Regional Directorate. Relational screening model was used. It was found that altruism behavior, peer support and leader support have a positive and significant effect on employee voice. In terms of demographic characteristics of the employees, it was seen that voice behaviors tend to significantly vary depending on job title and level of education.

Methodology

A survey research design was adopted. The description of facts and features about a population is the focus of the survey research. The purpose is to collect true, accurate, and systematic data, as well as to characterize the data and qualities of what is being examined. It is also beneficial due to the very large population from which the data was gathered. The structured questionnaire served as the primary source of primary data, which was complemented by interviews. The questionnaire was designed to correspond to the variables of the study as indicated in the hypotheses. The research was carried out in Enugu state, Nigeria's with focus on Juhel Pharmaceutical Company. The population for the study included all staff of Juhel Pharmaceutical, Enugu State. The total population is 806 while the sampling size is 264. The sampling size was obtained by using population statistical sampling formula by (Freund Williams 1986). A five point-Likert was applied in generating the data. The data collected with regards to each of the questions were analysed using in tables, frequencies, percentages, mean, and standard deviation and Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) versions 16.0 were used. To confirm the significance of the correlation between variables, Pearson correlation analysis was performed.

Data Presentation and Analyses

In this chapter efforts were made to present and analyses the data gathered; which were guided by the research questions already stated in chapter one. The data collected with regards to each of the questions were analysed using in tables, frequencies, percentages, mean, and standard deviation and ANOVA.

Data Presentation

Table 1: Distribution on Return Rate of Respondents

<i>Industries</i>	<i>Copies of questionnaire sent out</i>	<i>Copies of questionnaire returned</i>	<i>Copies of questionnaire not returned</i>	<i>Percentage of returned and verified copies</i>
<i>Senior Staff.</i>	62	51	11	19
<i>Others staff</i>	202	197	5	75
<i>Total</i>	264	248	16	94

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Data Analysis

Table 2: Altruism of employees has effect on the employees’ output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State

<i>STATEMENT</i>	<i>VGE</i>	<i>GE</i>	<i>UD</i>	<i>VLE</i>	<i>LE</i>	<i>MEAN</i>	<i>ST.DEV</i>
<i>Altruism has a positive effect on the employees’ output?</i>	74	87	37	30	20	3.7	21.049
<i>Altruism has a negative effect on the employees’ output?</i>	30	25	2	100	91	2.20	1.224
<i>Altruism does not have effect on the employees’ output?</i>	40	50	9	119	30	4.117	2.80

Source: Field Survey 2022

The response in table 2 reveals that 74 respondents to a very great extent believes that Altruism has a positive impact on the employees’ output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. 87 respondents believe to a great extent that it has a positive effect, 37 respondents were undecided, 30 respondents believe to a very less extents while 20respondents consider to a less extent. With a mean score of 21.747±21.049, the respondent is of the opinion that altruism has a positive effect on the employees’ output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. It is of the opinion that the altruism does not have a negative impact on the employees’ output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. This is predicated upon the mean score of 3.861±1.224 and the responses of 78 respondents to a very great extents suggest so, 57 respondents believe to a great extent, 21 respondents are undecided, 31 respondents to a very less extents believes while 41 respondents believe to a less extent that altruism has a negative effect on the employees’ output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. 11 respondents and 45 respondents to a very great extents and to a great extent believes respectively that altruism does not have any effect on the employees’ output of food and beverage of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. 89 respondents were undecided as to whether altruism does not have effect on the employees’ output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State.40 respondents and 33 respondents to a very less extent and to a less extent believes that altruism does not have effect on the employees’ output of food and beverage manufacturing firms with a mean score of 4.117±0.865.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

H₀: Sportsmanship does not have significant effect on employees’ job satisfaction of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State?

In testing the hypothesis, the data presented in table 4.2, was tested using regression analysis and the result is shown below.

Table 3: Summary of Regression Analysis for Hypothesis One

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.824	.589	.588		.33439
ANOVA					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	65.216	1	65.216	583.224	.000
Residual	102.427	916	.112		
Total	167.643	917			
COEFFICIENTS					
Model	Coefficient	Std. Error		T	Sig
Constant	1.958	.026		74.865	0.000
Sportsmanship	.335	.014		24.150	0.00

Source: SPSS Result, 2022

The result of the regression analysis summarized in table 6 shows that the model for the relationship Sportsmanship (SP) and sportsmanship has significant effect on the employees' job satisfaction food and beverage of manufacturing firms. $SP = 1.958 + 0.335HC$. This reveals that CP has a positive significant impact on the employees' job satisfaction of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state, Nigeria. Furthermore, the p -value < 0.05 indicates a significant effect/impact at 5% level of significance.

Also, the regression coefficient (R) of 0.824 indicates a strong positive relationship between the independent variable (Sportsmanship) and the dependent variable (employees' job satisfaction).

The coefficient of determination which is 0.589 reveals that 59% of the variation observed that the dependent variable is caused by the independent variable. The F value and the p -value (583.224, 0.000) shows that these results are significant. Based on this we can say that sportsmanship has significant impact on the employees' job satisfaction of food and beverage of manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Hypothesis Two

Ho: Altruism does not have significant effect on employees' output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

In testing the hypothesis, the data presented in table 3, was used tested using correlation analysis and the result is shown below.

Table 4: Pearson Correlation Coefficient

	Altruism	Output
Altruism	1	.903
Sig(1-tailed)	.918	.000
N		917
Altruism	.903	1
Output Sig(1-tailed)	.000	.918
N	917	

****Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).**

Table 4 presents the result from person product moment correlation. The correlation coefficient (R) between Altruism and employees' output is 0.903. This shows that there is a very strong positive relation between altruism and employees' output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State. This also indicates that when altruism increases, employees' output is enhanced. With p -values < 0.001 , this result is significant and did not occur by chance. Therefore, the results indicate that altruism have a strong positive relationship with employees' output of food and beverage of manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Discussion of the Findings

The result in objective one revealed that employee's sportsmanship (EM) has significant positive effect on the employees' job satisfaction of food and beverage manufacturing firms for the period. This demonstrates that if employees are encouraged, there will be more sportsmanship to improve employees' job satisfaction.

The result from objective two revealed that altruism of employees has significant impact on the employees' output of food and beverage manufacturing firms for the period. This shows that proper encouragement among team workers will go a long way in the performance of the firm.

Summary of Findings

The outcome of the analysis is as follows:

1. Sportsmanship has positively significant impact on employees' job satisfaction of food and beverage manufacturing firms with ($R=0.824$, $p\text{-value}<0.001$) while the F value and the p-value (583.224, 0.000) shows that these results are significant. Based on this we can say that sportsmanship has a positive effect on the employees' job satisfaction of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State?
2. Altruism has a positive impact on the employees' output of food and beverage manufacturing firms with ($R=0.903$, $p\text{-value}<0.001$) This implies that when altruism increases, employees' output is enhanced. With $p\text{-values} < 0.001$, this result is significant and did not occur by chance. Therefore, the results indicate that altruism has a strong positive relationship with the employees' output of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

Conclusion

Employee's extra role behavior is an important factor that can contribute positively to the performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state. Based on the finding, the study concluded that employee sportsmanship has significant effect on employees' job satisfaction and altruism of employee has significant effect on employees' output. Both has significant effect generally on the performance of food and beverage manufacturing firms.

Recommendation

1. Management should sustain the employee sportsmanship by motivating their staffs a means of holding on to the significant impact it has on the employees' job satisfaction of food and beverage manufacturing firms for the period.
2. Employee should continue on their altruism in order to improve on the position of employees' output. Also, to maintain willingness to assist new employees at work, and keep off from negative attitude.

Contribution to Knowledge

The study made incursions into the areas of employee sportsmanship and altruism of employee which was not previously explored by others researchers and it serve as the major component of employee's extra role behavior on the performance of food and beverage of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. This would add more flesh and develop the concepts of extra role behavior.

Reference

- Assam, A. P. (2002). Motivation and Job Satisfaction. (Unpublished MSc Dissertation) *University of Lagos, Nigeria*
- Bartol, K. (2006). Motivation. *Management (3rd Edi, pp 242-265), North Ryde: McGraw Hill.*
- Bateman, T. S. & Organ, D. W. (2015). Job satisfaction and the good soldier: The relationship between affect and employee citizenship. *Academy of Management Journal, 26, 587-595.*
- Becker, T. E & Kernan, M. C. (2016). matching commitment to supervisors and organizations to in-role and extra-role performance. *Human Performance, 16, 4, 327-348.*
- Campbell, J. P., McCloy, R. A., Oppler, S. H., & Sagar, C. E. (1993). A Theory of Performance. In N. Schmitt, W. C. Borman, and Associates (Eds.), *Personnel Selection in Organization: 35-69.*
- Cascio, W. (2003). Performance Management. *Managing Human Resources (5th Int. Edi.) Irwin/McGraw-Hill Publishers, p-300.*
- Chiboiwa, M. W., Chipunza, C., Samuel, M. O. (2011). Evaluation of job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behaviors: Case study of selected organizations in Zimbabwe. *African Journal of Business Management, 5, 2910-2918.*
- Daniel and Caryl, (1995). Exchange Variables as predictors of Job commitment and turnover. The impact of rewards cost alternation and investments, *Journal of Organizational Behavior and Human Performance, 27(2): 78-95.*
- Diah A. A. (2019). The Effect of Servant Leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior: The Role of Trust in Leader as a Mediation and Perceived Organizational Support as a Moderation. *Journal of Leadership in Organizations 1(1) 1-16, <https://jurnal.ugm.ac.id/leadership>*
- Diane M. B, Abbie J. S, Benson R. and Stacie A. F. (2013), Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Career Outcomes: The Cost of Being a Good Citizen. *Journal of Management, 39 (4); 958-984 <http://www.sagepub.com/journalsPermissions.nav>*
- Egwurudi, P.C., 2008. Job Satisfaction Effect on job characteristics, (Unpublished Msc Dissertation) University of Lagos, Nigeria.
- Erkubilay, C., Şentürk, F.K. (2020). The Effect of Altruism Behavior, Peer Support and Leader Support on Employee Voice. *Journal of Business Research-Turk, 12 (2), 1820-1833.*
- Evans, M. G. (2006). Organizational behavior: The Central Role of Motivation, *Journal of Management, 12(2): 203-207.*
- Eze, N., (2009). Sources of Motivation among Nigerian managers. *Journal of Social Psychology, 125(2): 341-345.*
- Hartt, A., et al. (2006). Behavior. Worm Book, The C. elegans Research Community, doi/10.1895/wormbook.1.87.1, <http://www.wormbook.org>.
- Hasan R., Mehmood A., and Syed M. Z. (2014). The Impacts of Employee's Job Performance Behavior and Organizational Culture on Organizational Productivity in Pharmaceutical Industries in Karachi. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business 5(12), 385-400.*
- Ibojo, O. B. and Asabi. O. M (2014). Compensation Management on Employees Performance in the Manufacturing Sector, A case study of A Reputable Food and Beverage Industry. *International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research (IJMSR) 2, (9), PP 108-117. www.arcjournals.org*
- Jibowo, A. A. (2007). Effect of Motivators and hygiene factors on job performance among extension workers organizations. in the former Western state of Nigeria. *The quarterly Journal of Administration, 12(1): 45-54.*
- Tung-Liang, H. (2014). The Relationships among Salary, Altruistic Behavior and Job Performance in the National Basketball Association. *International Journal of Business and Social Science, 5(9); 193-198.*
- Marija, K. (2022). Employee productivity in organization <https://clockify.me/blog/author/marija-kojic/>
- Maslow, Abraham H. (1970.) *Motivation and Personality: 2nd ed.* New York: Harper and Row.
- Mbah P. C, Ede T. E, & Ugochukwu, L. N. (2017). Effect of Organizational Citizenship behaviors on the performance of manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business Economics and Management Research 8, (12). www.skirec.org*
- Moorman, R. H. (1991). Relationship Between Organizational Justice and Organizational Citizenship Behaviors: Do Fairness Perceptions Influence Employee Citizenship. *Journal of Applied Psychology, 76(6), 845-855.*

- Nathan P. P, Brian D. B, Steven W. W., and Philip M. P. (2009), Individual- and Organizational-Level Consequences of Organizational Citizenship Behaviors: A Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 94 (1), 122–141.
- Nnamani E., Ozobu A, and Ejim E. P. (2015). Effect of Employee Motivation on Organizational Performance of selected manufacturing firms in Enugu State. *World Journal of Management and Behavioral Studies* 3 (1): 01-08.
- Natalie, L. S.; Christopher, B. & Hojun, S. (2020). Effects of Employees' Extra-Role Behaviors on Organizational Performance: An Assessment of Minor League Baseball Team Front Offices. *Journal of Global Sport Management*, 5(2); 1-18.
- Ogunyemi A. O. (2014). Influence of Employees 'Attitudinal Variables on Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Organizational Commitment. *Journal of Education and Practice* 5(22), 2222-1735
- Organ, D. W. (1988). Organizational citizenship behavior: The good soldier syndrome. Lexington, MA: Lexington Books.
- Organ, D. W., Podsakoff, M. P., MacKenzie, S. P. (2006). Organizational Citizenship Behavior: Its Nature, Antecedents and Consequences. London: Sage Publications.
- Porathe, P., Christine, (2009). How Toxic Colleagues Corrode Performance. *Harvard Business Review*, 87 (04).
- Robbins (1999). Essentials of Organizational Behavior, Prentice Hall, 5th Edition.
- Sekaran, U. & Bougie, R. (2016). Research methods for business: A skill building approach. John Wiley & Sons.
- Shengxian Y.; Na, W.; Shanshi. L. & Xiaoxiao, G. (2021). Job Insecurity and Employees' Extra-Role Behavior: Moderated Mediation Model of Negative Emotion and Workplace Friendship,
- Schnake, M. (1991). Organizational citizenship: A review, proposed model, and research agenda. *Hum. Relat.*, 44, 735-59.
- Schneider, B., Paul J. H., Brent D. S., and Amy N. S. (2013). Which Comes First: Employee Attitudes or Organizational Financial and Market Performance? *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 88(5) 836-851.
- Thompson, C., L. Beauvais and K. Lyness (1999). When work-family benefits are not enough: the influence of work-family culture on benefit utilization, organizational attachment and work family conflict. *Journal of Vocational Behavior* 54:392-415.
- Turnipseed, D. L. & Rassuli, A. (2005). Performance perceptions of organizational citizenship behaviors at work: a bi-level study among managers and employees. *British Journal of Management*, 16, 231-244.
- Zelenski, J. M., Steven A. M., and David A. J. (2017). The Happy-Productive Worker Thesis Revisited. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 9(4), 521-537.